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TH2LCRR is selectively activated during the first cell division of the human embryo.

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We studied gene expression in the human embryo immediately after fertilization and zygotic activation and at the first cell division from 1-cell to 2-cell stage. We describe here discovery of TH2LCRR as a zygotic cell factor required or important during the first cell division of the fertilized human embryo.

Citations

1. Li, Y.K., Zhang, X.X., Yang, Y., Gao, J., Shi, Q., Liu, S.D., Fu, W.P. and Sun, C., 2022. Convergent evidence supports TH2LCRR as a novel asthma susceptibility gene. American Journal of Respiratory Cell and Molecular Biology, 66(3), pp.283-292.